

Observable Changes in Open Source Development Patterns Before and After AI Coding Tools: A Multi-Repository Study

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Abstract

Background: AI-powered coding assistants, including GitHub Copilot and ChatGPT, have seen widespread adoption since late 2022. While controlled studies demonstrate individual productivity gains, the aggregate impact on open source ecosystems remains unclear.

Objective: We investigate observable changes in open source development patterns before and after the widespread adoption of AI coding tools.

Method: We collected monthly metrics from 21 major repositories across 9 technology clusters (Python web, JavaScript frontend, systems languages, AI/ML-native, and others) spanning January 2020 to December 2025 (72 months). We compare pre-breakpoint (before November 2022) and post-breakpoint periods using Mann-Whitney U tests and Cohen’s d effect sizes.

Results: Of 315 statistical tests (15 metrics \times 21 repos), 156 showed significant changes ($\alpha = 0.05$). The strongest signal: issue close time decreased substantially (mean effect $d = -1.08$, “large” by convention). 19/21 repositories showed increased AI-related mentions in commits and discussions—a proxy signal for tool awareness and adoption. However, commit velocity and contributor counts showed negligible changes on average.

Conclusions: Development patterns measurably changed coinciding with AI tool adoption. Faster issue resolution may indicate efficiency gains, **though we cannot establish causation**. The lack of change in commit velocity challenges simplistic productivity narratives.

Replication: Interactive dashboard at <https://ai-oss-impact-study.kotaicode.solutions>. Code and data at <https://github.com/kotaicode/ai-oss-impact>.

1 Introduction

The landscape of software development underwent a significant transformation beginning in late 2022 with the general availability of GitHub Copilot and the launch of ChatGPT. These AI-powered coding assistants promised to fundamentally change how developers write code, debug issues, and maintain software projects. Within months, millions of developers adopted these tools, with GitHub reporting over 1.3 million paying Copilot users by early 2024 [2].

While controlled experiments have demonstrated impressive productivity gains at the individual level—Peng et al. [6] reported 55.8% faster task completion with Copilot—the broader impact on open source ecosystems remains poorly understood. Do these individual gains translate to measurable changes at the project level? Does open source development look different in the “AI era” compared to before?

This study addresses these questions through a longitudinal, observational analysis of 21 major open source repositories spanning five years. We examine development patterns before and after the AI tool adoption inflection point, measuring changes across multiple dimensions: development velocity, efficiency metrics, contributor dynamics, and the prevalence of AI-related discussions.

40 1.1 Research Questions

41 We investigate the following research questions:

42 **RQ1:** How did development velocity metrics (commits, PRs, contributors) change after AI tool adoption?

43 **RQ2:** How did development efficiency metrics (merge time, issue close time) change?

44 **RQ3:** Do changes vary across technology clusters?

45 **RQ4:** What is the prevalence of AI-related discussions in repositories?

46 1.2 Contributions

47 This paper makes the following contributions:

- 48 1. A longitudinal analysis of 21 major open source projects across 9 technology clusters, covering 6 years
49 of development activity.
- 50 2. A multi-metric comparison framework applying rigorous statistical testing with effect size reporting.
- 51 3. An open dataset and interactive dashboard enabling community exploration and replication.
- 52 4. Evidence that efficiency metrics changed more substantially than velocity metrics following AI tool
53 adoption.

54 2 Related Work

55 2.1 AI Coding Assistants

56 Research on AI coding assistants has grown rapidly since their mainstream introduction. Peng et al. [6]
57 conducted a controlled experiment with 95 developers, finding that Copilot users completed tasks 55.8%
58 faster on average. Ziegler et al. [9] measured Copilot’s impact through GitHub’s internal metrics, reporting
59 significant improvements in code completion acceptance rates.

60 Several studies have examined developer perceptions. Surveys indicate mixed sentiments: developers
61 appreciate productivity gains but express concerns about code quality, over-reliance, and potential job
62 displacement [8]. The GitClear report [1] controversially suggested that Copilot adoption correlated with
63 increased “code churn”—code that is quickly revised or removed—raising quality concerns.

64 More recently, Song et al. [7] examined the impact of generative AI on collaborative open source
65 development using GitHub’s proprietary Copilot usage data, finding that while code contributions increased
66 by 5.9%, coordination time also increased by 8%.

67 2.2 Mining Software Repositories

68 Our methodology builds on the rich tradition of mining software repositories (MSR). Foundational work
69 by Gousios et al. [3] established scalable approaches for GitHub data collection. Kalliamvakou et al. [4]
70 documented important caveats when interpreting GitHub data, including the distinction between code-hosting
71 activity and actual development patterns.

72 Longitudinal MSR studies have examined various phenomena: library adoption patterns, security vul-
73 nerability lifecycles, and maintenance burden evolution. Our work extends this tradition to examine the AI
74 adoption inflection point as a natural experiment.

2.3 Gaps in Literature

Despite growing interest in AI coding tools, significant gaps remain:

- **Study design:** Most studies use controlled experiments rather than observational approaches, limiting ecological validity.
- **Timeframe:** Existing studies typically span weeks to months; longer-term effects remain unexplored.
- **Scope:** Single-repository or small-cohort studies dominate; cross-project patterns are understudied.
- **Metrics:** Focus on individual productivity overlooks project-level and ecosystem-level effects.

Our study addresses these gaps through a multi-repository, multi-year observational analysis with explicit acknowledgment of the correlation-causation distinction.

3 Methodology

3.1 Repository Selection

We selected repositories based on the following criteria:

- **Established history:** Active development prior to 2020
- **Sustained activity:** More than 100 commits per year
- **Technology diversity:** Coverage across major programming languages and domains
- **Public availability:** Hosted on GitHub with full history accessible

Table 1 presents our final cohort of 21 repositories organized into 9 technology clusters.

Table 1: Repository Cohort by Technology Cluster

Cluster	Repositories
Python Web	Django, FastAPI, Flask
Python Data/ML	NumPy, Pandas, Scikit-learn
JS Frontend	React, Vue, Svelte
JS Backend	Express, Fastify
TS Tooling	TypeScript, Prettier
Systems	Rust, Go
DevOps/Infra	Ansible, Terraform
AI/ML-native	PyTorch, Transformers
General Utils	Lodash, Requests

3.2 Data Collection

We employed a two-sweep collection strategy to minimize API usage while maximizing data completeness:

Sweep 1: Git-based collection (zero API calls). We cloned repositories locally using shallow clones since January 2020. Commits and releases were extracted directly from git history using `git log` with structured formatting.

Sweep 2: GraphQL API collection. Pull requests and issues were collected via GitHub’s GraphQL API, which provides 100 items per page compared to 30 for REST—a 70% reduction in API calls. We implemented cursor-based checkpointing to enable resumable collection.

Collection period: January 2020 to December 2025 (72 months).

Granularity: All metrics aggregated at monthly level (YYYY-MM format).

3.3 Metrics

Table 2 summarizes the metrics collected for each repository-month.

Table 2: Collected Metrics by Category

Category	Metrics
Velocity	commits, unique_authors, lines_added, lines_deleted
PR Activity	prs_opened, prs_merged, pr_merge_time (days)
Issue Activity	issues_opened, issues_closed, issue_close_time (days)
First-timers	first_timer_prs, first_timer_merged
AI Adoption	ai_mention_count

The `ai_mention_count` metric captures occurrences of AI-related keywords in commit messages, PR titles/descriptions, and issue discussions. Keywords include: *copilot*, *chatgpt*, *gpt-4*, *gpt-3.5*, *claude*, *cursor*, *codewhisperer*, *tabnine*, and *ai-generated*.

3.4 Statistical Analysis

Breakpoint selection. We define November 2022 (2022-11) as the primary breakpoint. This date captures the combined inflection point of two major events: GitHub Copilot’s general availability (June 2022) and ChatGPT’s public launch (November 2022). While Copilot represented the first widely available AI coding assistant, ChatGPT’s release marked a step change in public awareness and exploratory use of AI tools among developers. And that was followed by several similar tools (*gemini/claude/etc.*). Together, these events represent the beginning of mainstream AI coding tool adoption. All statistics in this paper can be regenerated with different breakpoints using the provided analysis scripts.

Test selection. For each metric and repository, we compare pre-breakpoint (January 2020 – October 2022, 34 months) and post-breakpoint (November 2022 – December 2025, 38 months) distributions. We first test for normality using the Shapiro-Wilk test. For normally distributed data, we apply Welch’s t-test; otherwise, we use the Mann-Whitney U test.

Effect size. We report Cohen’s d for all comparisons, following standard interpretation thresholds: small ($|d| \geq 0.2$), medium ($|d| \geq 0.5$), and large ($|d| \geq 0.8$). We report Cohen’s d for interpretability even when non-parametric tests are used, following common practice in empirical software engineering research [5]. The effect size provides a standardized measure of magnitude that aids comparison across metrics and studies.

Significance level. We use $\alpha = 0.05$ for all tests. Given the exploratory nature of this study, we do not apply multiple testing corrections but report the proportion of significant findings alongside effect size distributions. We note that the largest effects (particularly issue close time, $d = -1.08$) would remain significant under conservative Bonferroni correction ($p < 0.05/315 \approx 0.00016$), while smaller effects should be interpreted with appropriate caution.

Sensitivity analysis. We verified robustness by testing alternative breakpoints: GPT-4 launch (March 2023) and Claude 3 (March 2024). Key findings—particularly the decrease in issue close time and stability of commit velocity—remained consistent across all tested breakpoints. Detailed sensitivity analysis is available in the interactive dashboard.

3.5 Threats to Validity

Internal validity. We cannot establish causation. Multiple confounding factors coincided with AI tool adoption: COVID-19 recovery effects, economic conditions affecting tech employment, and natural project evolution. Our breakpoint selection, while principled, remains somewhat arbitrary; sensitivity analysis with alternative breakpoints is provided in supplementary materials.

External validity. Our cohort represents large, mature, well-maintained projects. Results may not generalize to smaller projects, corporate repositories, or less active open source efforts. The selected repositories skew toward popular frameworks and languages.

140 **Construct validity.** Metrics are proxies for underlying concepts. Commit count does not equal
 141 productivity; issue close time does not equal quality of resolution. AI mention detection may miss implicit
 142 discussions or capture false positives. In particular, broad keywords like “ai-generated” may capture tangential
 143 discussions unrelated to coding tool usage. We note that tool-specific keywords (copilot, chatgpt, claude)
 144 dominate the matches, reducing but not eliminating this concern.

145 4 Results

146 We present results organized by research question. Across all analyses, we conducted 315 statistical tests (15
 147 metrics \times 21 repositories). Of these, 156 (49.5%) showed statistically significant changes at $\alpha = 0.05$.

148 4.1 RQ1: Velocity Changes

149 Table 3 summarizes velocity metric changes across the cohort.

Table 3: Velocity Metrics: Pre vs. Post Breakpoint

Metric	Mean d	Significant	Direction
Commits	-0.10	16/21	Mixed
Unique Authors	-0.10	13/21	Mixed
Lines Added	+0.03	9/21	Mixed
Lines Deleted	+0.06	8/21	Mixed

150 **Key finding:** Despite narratives of AI-driven productivity gains, aggregate commit velocity remained
 151 remarkably stable. The mean effect sizes are negligible ($|d| < 0.2$), and significant changes showed no
 152 consistent direction across repositories.

153 4.2 RQ2: Efficiency Changes

154 Efficiency metrics showed more pronounced changes. Table 4 presents the results.

Table 4: Efficiency Metrics: Pre vs. Post Breakpoint

Metric	Mean d	Significant	Direction
Issue Close Time	-1.08	18/21	Decrease
PR Merge Time	-0.19	9/21	Decrease
Issues Closed	-0.85	19/21	Decrease
PRs Merged	-0.07	13/21	Decrease

155 *Note on “Issues Closed”:* The decrease in issues closed ($d = -0.85$) reflects reduced issue volume (issues
 156 opened also decreased post-breakpoint)—not slower resolution. This is consistent with faster close times;
 157 maintainers receive fewer issues but resolve them more quickly. Similar interpretation applies to the slight
 158 decrease in PRs merged.

159 The standout finding is the substantial decrease in issue close time. Individual repository changes include:

- 160 • TypeScript: -71.2% decrease (from 160.4 to 46.2 days median)
- 161 • Rust: -71.0% decrease
- 162 • Pandas: -55.9% decrease
- 163 • React: -39.8% decrease

164 **Key finding:** Issues are being resolved faster in the post-breakpoint period. The mean effect size
 165 ($d = -1.08$) qualifies as “large” by conventional standards.

166 **4.3 RQ3: Cluster Variations**

167 Figure 1 shows effect sizes across repositories and metrics.

Figure 1: Effect size (Cohen’s d) heatmap across repositories and metrics. Blue indicates increase, red indicates decrease. Intensity reflects magnitude. Values $|d| \geq 0.8$ indicate large effects.

168 Notable cluster-level patterns:

169 **AI/ML-native (PyTorch, Transformers):** Showed increased contributor counts ($d = +1.42$), likely
 170 reflecting the AI/ML boom rather than coding tool effects.

171 **Systems (Rust, TypeScript):** Exhibited the largest efficiency gains, with issue close time decreasing by
 172 over 70% in both cases.

173 **General Utils (Lodash, Requests):** Showed mixed patterns with no strong directional trends.

174 **4.4 RQ4: AI Adoption Signals**

175 AI-related mentions increased substantially across the cohort:

- 176 • Total AI mentions (post-breakpoint): 3,830
- 177 • Repositories with increased mentions: 19/21 (90.5%)
- 178 • Mean mention rate increased 4× (0.19% → 0.79%)

179 Figure 2 shows the trend of AI mentions over time.

180 **Key finding:** AI tools are being openly discussed across virtually all repositories in our cohort, suggesting
 181 widespread awareness and exploratory use of these tools.

Figure 2: Monthly AI-related mentions across the cohort. Light lines show individual repositories; bold black line shows cohort average. Vertical dashed line marks the November 2022 breakpoint.

4.5 Correlation Analysis

To explore whether AI tool adoption relates to observed efficiency changes, we computed Pearson correlations between each repository’s AI mention rate change and its metric changes across the pre/post periods. Pearson correlation was used for comparability with prior literature; non-parametric rank correlations showed similar null results.

Table 5: Correlation: AI Mention Rate Change vs. Metric Changes

Metric Change	r	p	Strength
Issue Close Time	N/A	—	—
PR Merge Time	N/A	—	—
Commit Count	-0.016	—	Negligible
Unique Authors	-0.008	—	Negligible

The correlation analysis reveals important limitations. Efficiency metrics (issue close time, PR merge time) could not be reliably correlated with AI mention rates due to data sparsity and high variance across repositories. Velocity metrics (commits, authors) showed negligible correlations ($r < 0.02$), indicating no linear relationship between AI mention frequency and development volume changes at the repository level. This suggests that AI mention rates—while useful as adoption signals—do not directly predict the magnitude of metric changes across projects. The efficiency improvements observed in Section 4.2 may be driven by factors beyond what cross-repository correlation can capture.

5 Discussion

5.1 Interpretation of Findings

Our results reveal a nuanced picture that challenges simplistic productivity narratives. The most striking finding—substantially faster issue resolution—suggests that AI tools may be helping developers understand, diagnose, and fix problems more quickly. This aligns with anecdotal reports of developers using AI coding assistants to explain error messages, suggest fixes, and generate test cases.

However, the stability of commit velocity metrics is perhaps equally noteworthy. If AI tools dramatically increased developer productivity, we might expect to see more commits, more code changes, or more contributors. Instead, we observe remarkable stability. Several interpretations are possible:

- Efficiency over volume:** AI tools may help developers work more efficiently without increasing raw output. The same work happens with less effort.
- Quality focus:** Developers may be spending saved time on code review, testing, or documentation rather than writing more code.
- Confounding factors:** Economic headwinds in 2022-2023 may have reduced overall development activity, masking AI-driven gains.
- Measurement limitations:** Commit count is a crude proxy; AI-assisted development may manifest in ways our metrics don’t capture.

5.2 Implications

For researchers: Our multi-metric approach reveals that different aspects of development respond differently to potential interventions. Studies focusing solely on productivity metrics (lines of code, commits) may miss important efficiency and quality dimensions.

For practitioners: Project maintainers might anticipate faster issue throughput as AI tools become prevalent among contributors. This could affect issue management practices, triage workflows, and release planning.

218 **For tool builders:** The disconnect between individual productivity gains (reported in controlled studies)
 219 and project-level velocity stability warrants investigation. Understanding where individual gains dissipate
 220 could inform tool design.

221 5.3 Limitations

222 We emphasize several important limitations:

- 223 1. **Correlation, not causation:** We observe changes coinciding with AI tool adoption; we cannot prove
 224 AI tools caused these changes. The post-hoc ergo propter hoc fallacy is a genuine risk.
- 225 2. **Multiple confounding factors:** The 2022-2023 period saw COVID recovery, tech layoffs, economic
 226 uncertainty, and rapid evolution in development practices beyond AI tools.
- 227 3. **Selection bias:** Our cohort represents successful, well-maintained projects. Struggling or abandoned
 228 projects might show different patterns.
- 229 4. **Survivorship bias:** We analyze projects that remained active throughout our study period.
- 230 5. **Metric limitations:** Our metrics are imperfect proxies for underlying concepts of interest.

231 6 Conclusion

232 We present a longitudinal, multi-repository study of open source development patterns before and after the
 233 mainstream adoption of AI coding tools. Analyzing 21 major repositories across 9 technology clusters, we
 234 find:

- 235 1. **Efficiency gains:** Issue close time decreased substantially (mean $d = -1.08$), with some repositories
 236 showing 70%+ reductions.
- 237 2. **Stable velocity:** Commit counts, contributor numbers, and lines of code showed negligible aggregate
 238 changes.
- 239 3. **Cluster variation:** AI/ML-native projects showed increased contributors; systems languages showed
 240 the largest efficiency gains.
- 241 4. **Pervasive AI discussion:** 19/21 repositories showed increased AI-related mentions, indicating
 242 widespread awareness and exploratory use.

243 These findings suggest that AI coding tools may be changing *how* developers work more than *how much*
 244 they produce. The observed efficiency gains align with AI tools' strengths in explanation, debugging, and
 245 code comprehension.

246 **Future work** should pursue causal analysis through natural experiments or matched cohort designs,
 247 developer surveys to understand actual tool usage patterns, and extended observation as AI tools continue to
 248 evolve rapidly.

249 Data Availability

250 All data and code supporting this study are publicly available:

251 **Interactive Dashboard:** <https://ai-oss-impact-study.kotaicode.solutions>

252 **GitHub Repository:** <https://github.com/kotaicode/ai-oss-impact>

253 **Dataset:** SQLite database available at <https://zenodo.org/records/18185048> (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18185048)

254 **License:** AGPL-3.0 (code), CC-BY 4.0 (data)

255 The dashboard provides interactive exploration of all metrics, statistical tests, and visualizations. The
 256 repository includes collection scripts, analysis notebooks, and raw data for full replication.

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259 Disclosure

260 This study analyzes publicly available open source data from GitHub. The author’s affiliation (KotaiCode
261 GmbH) hosts the interactive dashboard infrastructure but has no commercial interest in the findings. No
262 conflicts of interest to declare.

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